

HIGH-QUALITY HUMAN CAPITAL – THE FOUNDATION OF GREEN GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Given modern trends and emerging environmental problems, the transition to a 'green' growth model in our country is well-justified today. The formation of a 'green economy' is a complex process that affects all spheres of human activity, and the main condition for implementing its principles is high-quality human capital. This article examines the role and importance of human capital in ensuring the 'green' economic growth of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: «green economy», human capital, education, economic growth.

Introduction. The first half of the 21st century has been marked by the beginning of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, characterized by the active transition of countries to a 'knowledge economy' and a new model of industrial production. This model is based on advanced information and communication technologies (ICT) of the Fifth Technological Paradigm, and NBIC technologies (nanotechnology, biotechnology, information technology, and cognitive science) of the new Sixth Technological Paradigm

For a long period, economic growth in most countries was achieved through the irrational use of natural resources. In recent years, it has become evident that further economic growth without proper consideration of environmental factors poses threats to both current and future generations. Therefore, given the rapidly growing urgency of environmental and climate issues, the main characteristic of the new model of industrial production is the 'green' factor in the development of the global economy. Under these conditions, the primary task of Uzbekistan's economic development is to ensure 'green' growth. Thus, on January 30, 2025, in the 'Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy' the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On the State Program for the Implementation of the 'Uzbekistan – 2030' Strategy was issued. This decree aims to achieve a comprehensive 'green transformation' of industries and sectors, improve the quality of life of the population, and transition economic growth to a new 'green' development model [1].

Literature review. The relationship between human capital and the transition to a green economy has been studied by many authors worldwide. Professor Fortunata Ganda from Walter Sisulu University explored the economies of BRICS countries from 1990 to 2017 and concluded that human capital has positive impact on environmental sustainability [7]. In turn, a group of economists, Salim N., Shujah-ur-Rahman, and Jun Z., analyzing data from 1991 to 2014, found that human capital improves environmental quality by reducing the ecological footprint and carbon emissions [10].

Moreover, studying data from the People's Republic of China for the period 1991–2018, researchers Kai-Hua Wang, Muhammad Umar, Rabia Akram, and Ersin Caglar established a long-term relationship between green growth and human capital [13].

Bano S., Zhao Y., Ahmad A., Wang S., and Liu Y. accentuate education as a key aspect of human capital in their research. Using the example of the Republic of Pakistan, they concluded

that the accumulation of human capital can reduce carbon emissions and increase the rate of economic growth. [5].

Russian researchers Rutzky V.N. and Osipenko M.V. examined investments in human capital as a social aspect of the green economy [11]. Maryganova E.A. and Dmitrievskaya N.A. identified both positive and negative aspects of human capital impact on the environment [15]. As a positive aspect, they noted that a high level of human capital contributes to more efficient use of resources, the creation of their alternatives, as well as methods and approaches for environmental protection. On the other hand, the authors consider that the negative aspect is an anthropogenic impact on the environment due to the development of new technologies and population growth.

Some authors also highlight green human capital, which implies investments in the ecological intelligence of people [6]. The significance of green human capital is also noted by Liu Jia-Xin and Liu Bing [9].

In domestic science, despite a large number of studies in the fields of human capital and green economic development, the issues of the relationship and influence of human capital on green growth remain understudied.

Research methodology. The research method in this article was a theoretical analysis of scientific literature in the fields of human capital and green economy. The sample for this analysis included studies by domestic and foreign economists examining the influence and significance of highly developed human capital on ensuring the green growth of a country's economy. In the research process, methods of systemic approach, statistical, dynamic, structural, and comparative analysis were also applied to determine the relationship and influence of high-quality human capital on the formation and development of the country's green economy. The study utilized statistical materials from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as legislative and regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Analysis and results. To date, there is no universally accepted definition of a 'green economy,' but there is an understanding of its meaning. Thus, a green economy is understood as a model of economic development that implies responsible human attitudes toward natural resources. According to the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), a 'green economy' is defined as 'an economy that improves human well-being and ensures social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities' [14]. It can be said that the 'green economy' is a modern direction of economics aimed at reducing environmental threats and risks to improve human well-being and ensure social equality. Thereby, the 'green economy' is an economy that ensures the most rational use of natural resources; enhances natural capital; relies on alternative energy and renewable energy sources; and contributes to improving the quality of life of people.

The Green economy's formation is a complex process that affects the financial, economic, political, and social spheres of people's lives. Some scientists identify certain prerequisites that allow to create a favorable environment for its establishment and to initiate its development. One such condition facilitating the implementation of the standards and principles of a green economy is human capital, which, in a broad sense, represents the complex of knowledge, skills, and abilities used to meet the needs of individuals and society as a whole.

At the same time, it is important to consider the relationship between human capital and the need to transition to a green economy. On the one hand, the deterioration of the environmental situation leads to a decline in people's health, which is an integral component of human capital.

On the other hand, the development of green technologies capable of replacing elements of the brown economy without harming the country's economy requires a highly skilled, proactive, and creative workforce, whose the level of education and competence is also a part of human capital and drives the continuous process of scientific and technological progress.

According to Becker's definition, capital is managed by a person, which means that the development of a "green economy" as a more advanced way of conducting economic activity depends on the quality of human capital. Only highly developed human capital can competently and rationally distribute and use other types of capital (financial, production and natural), and thus ensure the effective and stable development of the country's economy.

Human capital and its cycles of growth and development are the main factors driving the innovation waves of the global economy and society [16]. Revolutionary changes in the economy and society, the largest innovations were carried out on the basis of accumulated human capital in each historical period of civilization's development.

It should be noted that countries, like Norway, Germany, Denmark, Japan, Finland, South Korea, etc., that successfully implementing the principles of a green economy, also have a high human capital index (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Countries' Ranking by Human Development Index in 2022 [8]

The Human Development Index calculations made by the United Nations Development Programme included 193 countries worldwide. The highest human capital index belongs to Switzerland, a country actively implementing the principles of green growth, reducing environmental impact, and transitioning to carbon neutrality. Second place in the ranking is held by Norway, where hydropower is actively used. Following are Iceland, Hong Kong, Denmark, Sweden, and Germany. It is worth noting that the European Union countries are pursuing a strategy of carbon neutrality by 2050. The Republic of Korea, in turn, is following the 'Green New Deal' plan, investing in green technologies and renewable energy sources. Japan is also actively introducing energy-saving technologies and waste recycling. The Republic of Uzbekistan has entered the group of countries with a high level of human capital development, with an index of 0.727, placing our country at 106th in the ranking.

Hereby, countries with a high human capital index are successfully implementing the green economy's concepts:

- Transition to renewable energy sources.
- Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.
- Sustainable use of natural resources.
- Development of a circular economy (recycling and reuse of waste).
- Investments in green technologies and innovations.

It means that human capital plays a crucial role in the green economy's formation and leads to a conscious choice of a green lifestyle, where the population takes responsibility for preserving the environment. Through a high level of human capital, the 'green economy' becomes ingrained in human consciousness and becomes part of their way of life. The table below shows groups of countries by level of human development

Table 1

Groups of Countries by Level of Human Development

Groups of Countries	Human Development Index (HDI)	Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI)	Gender Development Index (GDI)	Gender Inequality Index (GII)
Countries with a very high level of human development	0,902	0,807	0,988	0,150
Countries with a high level of human development	0,764	0,628	0,962	0,339
Countries with a medium level of human development	0,640	0,447	0,870	0,476
Countries with a low level of human development	0,517	0,341	0,868	0,579

It is known that countries such as Japan, South Korea, Singapore, Switzerland, and others, which successfully practice 'green' development, perceive a shortage of certain natural resources and therefore they are forced to import most of resources from abroad. This is compensated by a high level of human capital, meaning that even with limited natural resources, a high level of development can be achieved through innovation, technology, and effective management. Often, such countries have a large number of prestigious and globally recognized research centers. Some

experts note that in some cases, the deficit or absence of natural resources serves as an incentive for the development of human capital and, consequently, for the green growth of the economy.

There are a number of environmental problems in Uzbekistan, as in many countries around the world. For example, carbon dioxide emissions, dependence on fossil fuels, water and air pollution, waste management and recycling issues, and others. In turn, the development and accumulation of high-quality human capital will help resolve these accumulated problems and achieve significant success in the field of the green economy.

The American economist S. Kuznets also noted that there is a minimum threshold of accumulated national human capital, without which the transition to the next technological stage of the economy is impossible or highly unlikely. [12].

In the modern world, investments in knowledge are growing at a rapid pace. Knowledge plays an important role in the innovative development of the economy, which, in turn, leads to the growth of high-tech industries based on intellectual labor. Economic modernization, intellectual capital, evidence-based medicine, increased labor productivity, and the value of human labor are all results of investments in human capital. In this regard, the accumulation of human capital and the improvement of its quality play a decisive role in the transition to a green economy as a more advanced way of conducting economic activities.

To improve the quality of human capital, investments in the development of healthcare, culture, education, and science centers are necessary. However, one of the main areas for enhancing the quality of human capital is education. It is in the learning process, at all stages and in any modern format, that the necessary competencies are created. Ultimately, scientific and educational centers will determine the quality of human capital, which, in turn, will determine the economic development and prosperity of the country.

The training of advanced, creatively thinking personnel and enhancing their competitiveness in accordance with labor market demands are directly linked to the process of university education. In this regard, serious attention is being paid in the republic to the quality organization of higher education, as well as to studying and implementing the systems and experiences of foreign countries. In recent years, through numerous reforms in the education system, access to higher education has steadily increased.

Figure 2. Dynamics of higher education organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan [17]

In order to fundamentally improve the higher education system and ensure the necessary conditions for training specialists with higher education in accordance with international standards, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Measures for the Further

Development of the Higher Education System' was adopted on April 20, 2017 [4]. This influenced the change in the number of higher education institutions starting from 2018. Starting from 2018, there has been a sharp increase in the number of higher education institutions. If in 2017 this value was 72, by 2018 it had increased to 119, and by 2023 it reached 219.

Highly skilled scientists and engineers are essential for the development of areas such as renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and clean technologies. A qualified and knowledgeable workforce is capable of conducting research and developing new technologies that reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improve resource efficiency, and protect the environment. This requires a high level of knowledge, experience, and creativity, which can only be achieved through investments in education and training.

In order to create conditions for the full development of intellectual capital and to identify priority areas for the systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a Decree 'On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.' Within the framework of this Decree, a Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was developed. Its strategic goal is to improve the quality of training highly qualified personnel and to develop human capital based on labor market requirements for the modernization and stable socio-economic development of the country. This, in turn, will positively impact on the intellectual capital of the country, which is a significant component of the 'green' economy [3].

The damage to the environment and human health is caused not by production growth itself, but by outdated capacities and technologies. Their modernization is an integral part of the policy of innovative modernization and accelerated economic growth. At the same time, high growth rates have a positive impact on the state of the environment due to the reduction of specific emissions of pollutants. The latter, in turn, is related to the fact that with appropriate investment activity, the quality of growth improves, implying an increase in the qualitative parameters of the population's standard of living

Therefore, in December 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Measures to Improve the Effectiveness of Reforms Aimed at Transitioning the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Green Economy by 2030' was adopted. Within its framework, the Program, Concept, and Action Plan for the Transition to a Green Economy and Ensuring Green Growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 were approved. The target parameters for ensuring green growth in Uzbekistan are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Target Indicators for Transitioning to a Green Economy and Ensuring Green Growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030 [2]

N	Indicators	Measurement	2022	2024	2026	2028	2030
1.	Reduction in energy intensity per unit of gross domestic product (relative to 2021)	%	5,0	14,0	22,0	27,0	30,0
2.	Energy consumption in industry, share of total energy consumption.	%	26,0	25,0	23,0	21,0	20,0
3.	Increase in the share of renewable energy sources in total electricity production (including hydropower)	%	8,0	9,0	24,3	29,0	30,5
		kw/h	6,5	8,6	25,0	34,0	40,7
4.	Construction of small-scale solar photovoltaic power plants	MW	10,0	150,0	400,0	800,0	1500,0

5.	Population with access to improved drinking water sources as a percentage of the total population	%	69,7	80,93	87,12	88,5	90,0
6.	Increase in tree and shrub stocks on forest fund lands	Mln cub/m	64,2	68,1	77,0	85,5	92,3
7.	Expansion of urban green zones under the 'Green Edge' project (as a percentage of the total area of the settlement).	%	8,3	12,4	15,8	23,8	30,0
8.	Establishment of 600 new waste collection points in the regions.	units	-	50	200	400	600

To ensure the achievement of the target indicators outlined in the table, an Action Plan for the Transition to a Green Economy and Ensuring Green Growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was developed. One of the key points for achieving green growth is 'Building Capacity and Developing Human Capital within the Framework of Green Growth.' In this section of the Action Plan, all measures are aimed at fostering environmental awareness among people, manifested in an increased sense of responsibility for nature conservation. This is achieved by integrating the principles and key patterns of the green economy and green growth into educational curricula and practices within educational institutions.

Conclusion and recommendations. In the face of global challenges such as climate change and economic upheavals, Uzbekistan must actively develop its human resources, embrace innovation, and invest in a sustainable future.

The formation of high-quality human capital is a substantial factor for the development of renewable energy sources, which contributes to green economic growth and ensures the country's energy independence. Investing in education and enhancing the knowledge and skills of the people, will facilitate the creation of high-tech production of innovative products. Thereby forming competitive advantages alongside natural resources, technologies, and information to foster an innovative and sustainable economy.

In our opinion, to achieve "green" economic growth in the country, it is necessary:

- to ensure further development and improvement of the structure of higher education;
- to establish a system of environmental education and enlightenment, that capable of shaping environmental consciousness among citizens;
- to integrate environmental principles into training and retraining programs;
- to create and enhance the prestige of professions in the environmental sector;
- to use public actions in solving environmental issues.

Thus a green economy, shaped by high-quality human capital, could define modern economic development and prosperity not only for the country but also for its citizens.

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